

Semantic Structure of Noun Units with the General Name "Honesty"

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the semantic structure of noun units with the general term "Honesty". In the process of analysis, the meanings of lexemes in the Uzbek language in various speech processes are studied. Semasiology is one of the most important achievements of linguistics. In the process of analyzing semantic structures, noun units with the meaning "Honesty" found in various artistic and scientific sources are studied.*

Key words: *Semasiology, semantic structure, lexeme, sema.*

INTRODUCTION

Speech is one of the important aspects that reflect the spiritual qualities of a person. A spiritual diagnosis of a person's spirituality through speech is a complicated process. For example, the presence of words and phrases belonging to the lexical category of "*spirituality*" in the speech of the creator to prepare a text reflecting the main character of an artistic work and his level of perfection creates a basis for describing how perfect a person the hero is. For example, one of the important adjectives related to the lexical category "*spirituality*" is the common noun "*honesty*". In order to deeply analyze the semantic structure of this spiritual group, first of all, it is necessary to give explanations of some scientific terms related to linguistics. For example, we will pay attention to how the concepts of sema, semema, lexical category or semantic structure are interpreted in linguistics and the definitions given to them in various sources. Lexical meaning is an abstract phenomenon that is difficult to interpret. In his textbook "*Hozirgi adabiy o'zbek tili*", Shavkat Rahmatullayev stated that one of the most important and effective achievements of 20th century linguistics was the discovery of the method of component analysis, that is, the study of lexical meaning by dividing it into parts.¹ The method of component analysis is also called the method of seminal analysis. Therefore, the interpretation of the meanings of lexemes by dividing them into symbols is the interpretation of the meaning by relating it to reality. Sema is derived from the Greek word sema - "sign" and is studied from a broad concept to a narrow one.²

Commenting on the semantic structure is a complex phenomenon in linguistics that can be analyzed from different perspectives of the language. As mentioned in Muhayyo Hakimova's manual "*Semasiology*", the main unit of the lexical-semantic system of the language is a word or lexeme with a lexical meaning. In this article, we will analyze what kind of lexemes and words with lexical meaning of the noun units with the symbol "*honesty*" are expressed.³ In the process of analysis, various works of art and dictionaries covering different areas of the language are used. The general

¹ Sh. Rahmatullayev "Hozirgi adabiy o'zbek tili" textbook - Tashkent: "Universitet", 2006, page 50.

² "An explanatory dictionary of the main concepts of spirituality". - Tashkent: Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam, 2010. -B. 744

³ Muhayyo Hakimova. "Semasiology" study guide. -Tashkent, 2008. 31 p.

meaning of the noun "honesty" is analyzed through examples of how units are expressed by different lexemes and which lexemes can be combined with other words into a lexical category. Below, the semantic structure of noun units with the general meaning of "honesty" is analyzed. In terms of systematically analyzing the meanings of each unit and words that form a combination with the lexeme of honesty.

If we dwell on the meanings of the lexeme "to do something honestly" listed in the "Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language", this lexeme has its own and portable meanings.⁴ This lexeme is used in the sense of "to do honestly, to do what one can eat and drink". It is used figuratively and on the basis of syntagmatic relationship in the sense of justifying something and doing something worthy of it. For example, if we talk about the combination "the lexeme "do something honestly" is used in this combination in a figurative sense, i.e. "to make mother satisfied for the mother's milk, to do something worthy of it." Also, if we pay attention to another combination found in this dictionary, i.e., "to make the hand honest", in this combination, the lexeme of the hand is not in its meaning (the name of a part of the human body), rather, combined with the lexeme "honest", it means "circumcision"(in uzbek language "sunnat qilmoq"). As an example, a passage from Togai Murad's story "Ot kishnagan oqshom" was quoted: "Shoymardon is the head of the farm, he made his son's hand honest."

If we dwell on the explanation of the phrase "make a living with honesty" mentioned in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Basic Concepts of Spirituality", this phrase means a wide and very different meanings.⁵ First of all, this combination means "making a living with one's own work", and if we analyze it more deeply, it means "not betraying one's deposit, patting orphans on the head, giving a devotion from one's own property, repaying debts on time. Of course, these semes appear in various speech processes and syntagmatic relations with other lexemes.

In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" the meaning of the lexeme "honest" used in the field of sports is mentioned. This lexeme is used in world arenas as an international term. The lexeme "Honest", which is one of the methods of struggle, is indirectly related to the category of spirituality with the meanings of "achieving pure victory, winning without any harsh methods", "achieving superiority". As an example, a sentence from Nazar Eshankul's "Yalpiz hidi" is quoted: - Honest! - shouted Sharif the rider. - It's called knocking it down! In this text, this lexeme also means "honor, pride, pure victory", "honor of youth", "obvious superiority".

Below we will focus on the explanation and analysis of some words that can be synonymous with the lexeme "Honest". The word "pure" found in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" is synonymous with the word "honest" when it is used in some places, that is, in a figurative sense, can produce. If we define the literal and figurative meanings of the lexeme "pure", the literal meaning of the lexeme is "pure, immaculate, clean". As an example of this theme, we can cite Erkin Vahidov's description of the morning as "pure" in his poem "Boychechak". One of the other meanings of the word "pure" is "noble, clean, unmixed with other elements". For example, we can cite as an example the combination "pure gold" that is often found in our language. This lexeme is used synonymously with the word "honest" in some speech processes, and in this case, the lexeme "pure" is used in the figurative sense, i.e. "untainted, free from any fault, clean and pure". For example, A. Mukhtar used this lexeme in the meaning of "honest": "What do I have to do with the people of this market, the pure and the impure, the two-faced crowd here?" (Asarlar). In this case, the combination of "pure and impure servants" describes people who are honest or "impure", who "make a living in a wrong and dishonest way". In fact, we can see the use of words such as "pure", "purity", "sincere" in relation to people who live with honesty. It is clear that when we come across an honest human combination, we imagine a person who "gives a favor" to others, "helps the needy".

⁴ An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language: more than 80,000 words and phrases. J. I. - Tashkent: UzME, 2022.

⁵ "Annotated dictionary of the main concepts of spirituality" - Tashkent: Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam, 2010, p. 744.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the lexeme of honesty is a directly and indirectly related unit that means the same lexeme in different speech contexts in artistic works and explanatory dictionaries. Alibek Rustamov in his book "Soʻz xususida soʻz", the ability to call something in different ways in the language, the use of native and figurative meanings of words in the process of speech is a unique art he said.⁶ In this article, the lexical-semantic category "spirituality" is analyzed based on the syntagmatic relation of the common-semantic lexeme "honesty" and the semantically related lexical system. We have seen that the word "Honesty" is used in various fields in our language. In fact, we can see that their semantic possibilities are wide when their meanings related to different fields are used by language users in different speech processes. Also, in addition to the explanations of the nouns with the meaning of "honesty", the explanations of the meanings of the synonyms used as synonyms of the lexeme "honest" are specific for different meanings. . By deeply analyzing the examples and sentences mentioned above, we can see that a lexeme has very wide and rich semantic possibilities.

References

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⁶ Alibek Rustamov "Soʻz xususida soʻz" - Tashkent: "Yosh gvardiya", 1987.